

High Performance Hypereutectic Al-Si alloys Developed for Metal Additive Manufacturing

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Abstract: Metal additive manufacturing (AM), especially powder bed fusion (PBF) has already matured from lab development into industrial implementations nowadays and can be found in most demanding applications. Despite these advancements, the additive manufacturing of aluminium alloys has remained largely limited to Al–Si casting alloys near the eutectic composition, such as AlSi10Mg. In this work, we present the development of a new class of hypereutectic Al–Si alloys tailored for AM, along with the powder production, corresponding PBF process parameters, resulting material properties, and potential applications. The alloy set includes binary AlSi20 and AlSi40 compositions, as well as a multicomponent AlSi18FeMnCr alloy. High-quality, spherical metal powder for each alloy was produced with gas atomization at Future Materials Catapult Center. The process, equipment and learnings from powder production will be presented. With increasing Si content, the linear coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) decreases and can approach that of selected steels and copper alloys. Such CTE compatibility enables the potential substitution of these heavier materials in multi-material assemblies. The hypereutectic Al–Si alloys developed here also demonstrate superior retention of mechanical strength after high-temperature annealing compared with the conventional AlSi10Mg alloy. In particular, the AlSi18FeMnCr alloy exhibits excellent high-temperature strength, making it a promising candidate for applications requiring lightweight components that maintain mechanical integrity at elevated temperatures.